

An Analytical survey of Stock trading & Investor Preferences, with Special reference to rural areas of Jaipur District

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Introduction:

The Indian economy aspires to become a 5 trillion dollar economy by the year 2025. In making the Indian economy a 5 trillion dollar economy the role of rural investors will be of utmost importance. The author has noticed that the education, skill development, better infrastructure, access to markets, credit availability in rural areas and liberalization of the State's economy as the key factors are responsible for steadily shifting of rural workforce in favour of non-farm activities. This study will be represents on evolution and impact of stock trading in rural areas of Jaipur District.

Development of the rural sector in state has always been a matter of great concern of our plans. Moreover, the rural youth, who is more educated and aware, aspires for employment that suits their skills and knowledge. The rural youth is hesitant to follow the footprints of their forefathers as they don't see promising future in agriculture. Despite these factors, the overall growth targets for the economy may be extremely difficult to achieve without the growth of agriculture. This study tries to survey and analyse the role of stock broking and investors preferences of rural investors comprises comprehensive multidimensional and multisectoral concept.

Stock Trading in Rural Jaipur: Challenges and Prospects

An increased saturation in the larger metros and greater availability of disposable income coupled with changing attitudes towards equity markets in smaller towns have caused stock brokers to focus on the latter for their expansion plans.

There are significant opportunities in the northern regions as well as pockets in the south and the east, according to industry experts. Brokerages are expanding not just to Tier-II and Tier-III cities and beyond.

The biggest cities such as Mumbai and Delhi are known as Tier-I cities and others are classified in decreasing order depending on various parameters such as commercialization and population. The routes of expansion for brokerages in these areas are also two-fold, setting up their own branches or entering through the franchisee route.

Profile of Stock Brokers

The expansion process does not have an entirely smooth run since non-metro areas can have certain limitations. This study is focused upon the challenges and prospects of Stock Broker in Rural Jaipur and adjoining areas.

Research Methodology

The study is designed as a descriptive one based on both secondary and primary data.

Primary Data

The primary data necessary for the study has been collected from the people of Rural Jaipur and adjoining areas of city. The household sector of the Rural Jaipur is the population frame fixed for the study. Since the size of the household sector 5 lacs is very large, population survey is not possible. Hence sample survey has been carried out.

Sources of secondary data

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The secondary data necessary for the study have been collected from the following sources:

1. Publication - Directorate of Economics & Statistics, Rajasthan
2. Publications of National Council for Applied Economic Research.
3. Hand book of statistics of Indian Economy, Reserve Bank of India.
4. SEBI Bulletins.
5. Publications of Central Statistical, Organization.
6. Publications of BSE India
7. Reports from various advisory agencies
8. Publications of the Director of Economics and Statistics,
9. Periodicals and Journals like Economic Times, Capital Market, Business India, etc and
10. Various Websites.

Sampling Design

A stratified random sampling procedure is adopted for the selection of sample informants.

Rural Jaipur is firstly divided in to two parts; one is the semi-urban area and second is adjoining areas like Phulera, Bassi, Jamwa Ramgarh, Virat Nagar, Shahpura and Kotputli tehsils. Semi-urban area consists of all population resides in city with various backgrounds and ethnic groups. Selection of adjoin areas was based on the inclination of residents towards investment and equity with a mix of rural and industries oriented locations.

In the second stage from semi-urban area researcher has selected the prominent locations where we can interact all types of masses to understand their inclinations towards the investment. In the third stage, from each of the adjoining areas rural tehsil were selected. In the fourth stage, six tehsils were selected and 75 households each were identified. Thus 450 households were originally taken as the sample of which 142 households were neither

responded nor given full information to the researcher. Full information has obtained from 308 households only. Hence these 308 households form the actual sample for the survey.

Analysis and Interpretation

The Following factors are studied to understand the potential.

Sex wise distribution of Brokers

Majority of the stockbrokers firms / franchisee in the Rural Jaipur are males which are dominant in this industry. The sample survey shows that 82% members are males and only 18% are females.

Only a few of them do active business. The distribution pattern follows the general trend of fewer women participation in business and allied activities.

Age-wise Distribution of Stockbrokers

Age-wise distribution of brokers shows domination in favour of the middle-aged group.

It is found that 58% of brokers belong to the age group of 41-50 followed by 23% belonging to the age group of above 50 category. Age Group 31-40 represents 15 % of membership. An interesting revelation of the study is that young talents are not attracted to this profession. Taking into account the long-term growth and development of the exchange, young talents are to be attracted to take membership of the exchange or related services.

Educational Qualification of Brokers

To be successful in the field of brokerage service, brokers need to have in-depth knowledge about stock market activities and operations. A minimum level of education is a must for brokers. In study it is found that the majority of them (66%) are graduates, followed by postgraduates constituting 22 % and undergraduates 8%.

These educated brokers are a powerful force to reckon with and they can be utilized fruitfully in the area of investor education.

Primary Market Operations

The primary market is the market for new issues of stocks and shares. Operation in the primary market is very important on account of the fact that funds are mobilized initially from the primary market.

The sample survey shows that 68% of the brokers have primary market operations. The majority of brokers collect application forms of primary issues from the exchange. There are others who collect the application forms directly from the respective company and merchant bankers.

Regarding the disinterest of some brokers in primary market operation, they say that investors normally ask for completion and deposit of application forms to banks and they are not willing to undertake. They state that they have to employ additional staff for this purpose resulting in increased management expenses.

Brokerage in Primary Market

It is found that 60% of the brokers have the opinion that brokerage is adequate. Though 40% of brokers say that the brokerage is inadequate, it is substantial. Brokers generally opined that they get a commission of just 1% plus some incentive on the basis of the volume of business generated. This may be due to the reason that the issuing companies may be spending a part of the amount earmarked for brokerage for meeting some other issue expenses.

Evaluation of Primary Issues of Capital

Brokers are supposed to be experts in the field of stock market activities. Investors may approach the brokers for specific guidance and expert advice about the prospects of a particular company and its public issue of shares.

It is found in study that most of the brokers (70%) evaluate primary issues for the purpose of providing consultancy and rest (30%) not able to provide the same.

Accuracy level of evaluation

Depending upon the expertise and ability of brokers, they have different levels of accuracy in evaluating securities.

The survey shows that at the accuracy level of 0-25 percent, there are no brokers.

In the 26-50 category, 30% brokers, followed by 50% brokers in 51-75 Category.

The other 25 percent of brokers fall under 76-100 category.

There is a strong need for improving the accuracy level of evaluation by brokers.

If the investors, depending on the positive evaluation made by brokers, apply for shares and later on result in loss, they may turn away from primary market investment. This is not good in the long-term perspective of the capital market.

Secondary Market Operations

When the primary distribution of security issues has been completed, some investors may exercise the option of selling the securities. Those investors who fail to get allotment of securities may decide to purchase the securities. Investors who intend to sell the securities and those who want to buy the securities approach the respective stock exchange where these shares are dealt in. The stock exchange provides the facility to execute the transactions. Thus the secondary market takes shape In the secondary market, transactions of securities which have already been issued and listed or which are in the permitted list of securities of the exchange are traded.

Acceptance of Recommendation in the Secondary Market

Though brokers often recommend shares from the secondary market to be bought by investors, the responses of investors in most cases are not encouraging.

It is found that only 18% of brokers get full acceptance of recommendation by clients. 52% of broker's recommendations are not always accepted by clients.

30% of broker's recommendations are not at all accepted by clients.

The reasons for such poor response on the part of investors may be due to-

- a. Poor quality of consultancy service,
- b. Past bitter experience of investors,
- c. Unreliable data being used by brokers,
- d. Untimely extension of consultancy service etc.

Brokerage in Secondary Market

Brokers charge a commission on each purchase and each sale, which they execute on behalf of their clients. In order to fulfill their function and earn commission, brokers must develop their business and provide an office with adequate financial information services, current quotation facilities and advisers to enable investors to make the decisions upon which they act.

Maximum Brokerage that can be charged for trading done on stock exchanges in India has an upper limit of 2.5%. Although, it is commonly believed that maximum brokerage limit is fixed by SEBI, this is done by Stock Exchanges. Maximum brokerage that can be charged by its members is decided by concerned exchange and is mentioned in the Bye-Laws of the Exchange.

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